

Study Mechanical, Swelling and Dielectric Properties of Prehydrolysed Banana Fiber – Waste Polyurethane foam Composites

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SUMMARY:

Production of composite from polyurethane foam waste by using prehydrolysed banana fibers treated or untreated by maleic anhydride.

Esterification of banana fibers by using maleic anhydride reduces swelling and improve both mechanical strength and dielectric properties of composite.

Addition of aluminum silicate exhibited enhancements in its dielectric properties at constant lower than 10%. While, abrupt increases can be seen in the dielectric constant (ϵ') and dielectric loss (ϵ'') for samples contain more than 7.5% aluminum silicate. IR and scanning electron microscopy were studied.

Keywords: Lignocellulose composite; Banana fibers; polyurethane; Maleic anhydride; Aluminum silicate.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to increase demand of wood ultimately results in the erosion of environment, many efforts have been directed to the employment of natural cellulose [1]. Banana fiber which is a lignocellulosic material, relatively inexpensive and abundantly available was assessed in terms of its fiber-matrix adhesion [2].

The hydroxyl – rich nature of natural lignocellulosic suggest they are particularly useful in thermosetting system such as polyurethane. Polyurethane serves as crosslinking agent and as a good electrical insulation [3, 4]. Addition of fillers such as carbon black or silica increased the electrical insulation of the composite [5].

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

-Banana fibers, Waste polyurethane, maleic anhydride and Aluminum silicate .

2.2. Treatment of Banana Fiber

The fibers were esterified by using 2% maleic anhydride in xylene. The fibers stirred properly in maleic anhydride solution for 20 minutes, then left for 18 hr. at room temperature. The fibers were filtered and dried in an oven at 60°C till constant weight [1].

2.3. Preparation of the composite

A specific amount of ground sample was then impregnated in polymer solution. After that the mixture should be stirred properly and kept at room temperature for 24 h. The homogeneous mixture was then processed as follows: 50 g dry sample were placed in a disc form, diameter 15 cm, heated to 150C°, and then pressed under 25 and 50 KN disc for 5 min.

2.4. Measurements

The composite samples were subjected to the following measurements.

2.4.1. Water Absorption

Water absorption percent can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Water absorption \%} = \frac{W_w - W_i}{W_i} \times 100$$

Where W_i and W_w are the initial and wet weights of the composites, respectively. This test was measured according to the method of D 570 -81 ASTM [6].

2.4.2. Bending strength

Bending strength is defined as the maximum load should be applied to the sample to be broken and can be calculated by the following relation:

$$\text{Bending Strength} = \frac{3pL}{2bd^2} \text{ N/mm}^2$$

Where p is the maximum bending load, L is the length of span, b is the width of specimen and d is the thickness of specimen.

2.4.3. Infrared Spectra

The samples were measured as KBr discs by using apparatus Jocco FTIR spectrophotometer, Japan.

2.4.4. Scanning electron microscopy

Specimens were conducted on JEDL JEM-100 S electron microscope using the gold – Sputtering technique.

2.4.5. Dielectric measurements

The dielectric constant (ϵ') and dielectric loss (ϵ'') can be calculated as following:

$$\epsilon' = \frac{C d}{\epsilon_0 A}$$

$$\epsilon'' = \epsilon_0 \tan \delta$$

Where C is the capacitance of the measured sample in Farad, d is the sample thickness in meter; A is the cross section area of sample. ϵ_0 is the permittivity (dielectric constant) of air = $8.85 \times 10^{-12} \text{ Fm}^{-1}$. $\tan \delta$ is the loss tangent or the dissipation factor.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Effect of treatment and polyurethane concentrations

It can be seen from Table [1] that the treated composite with maleic anhydride showed higher strength properties and lower water absorption comparing with that obtained for the untreated composite. This results from that the maleic anhydride is used as a coupling agent contains functional groups which have capability to react with the fiber and polymer. In addition, hydrogen bonding has been formed that improve the fiber – matrix reaction [7].

It is also seen from Table [1] for both untreated and treated composites, as the polymer concentrations increased, their strength properties showed increase. On the other hand, it was found that as the polymer concentration increases, percentage of water absorption for both composites showed decrease. The noticeable effect of polyurethane concentration on properties of the composites originates from that polymer has a thermoplastic property, which may serve as a binder to the banana fiber composite. So, by increasing polymer concentration, the binder becomes much stronger due to formation of additional hydrogen bonds and consequently increasing of the internal bond [8].

Table [1]: Properties of composites prepared from banana fiber treated or untreated by maleic anhydride with waste polyurethane foam

Composite	Polymer %	Strength properties		Water Absorption					
				After immersion in boiling water		After immersion in water for 24 h		After immersion in water for 7 days	
		Bending strength N/mm ²	Modulus of elasticity N/mm ²	W %	T %	W %	T%	W %	T%
Untreated Composite	10%	7.9	1480.5	41.2	25	40	26.5	44	27.8
	20%	8.8	2080	36	17.3	35	18	38	20
	30%	11.6	2250.7	32	14	29.2	16	33	16
Treated Composite	10%	10.1	2050.3	40	23.2	36	20.6	40	25
	20%	11.3	2640.2	35	14.1	32	14.3	36	15.3
	30%	15.3	2830	25	11.5	22.9	11.5	30	11.5

Where W is expressed as a weight and T is a thickness Pressure = 50 KN.

3.2. Effect of compression on the treated composite containing 20 % polyurethane

Table [2] show that the strength properties of the treated composite are increased more twice if the pressure increased from 25 to 50 KN in addition decreasing of water absorption by approximately 60 %. As a result, the strength properties of the treated composite are strongly affected by compression. Such result obtained at higher pressure (50 KN) and measured at 150°C. In other words, increasing the pressure

makes the fibers or particles of composite combine strongly with polymer due to its formation of strong chemical bond between the reinforcement and matrix. This in turn leads to more compact composite with higher density i.e. higher internal bond and consequently higher strength properties with lower water absorption [4].

Table [2] Effect of pressure on the properties of the treated composite by maleic anhydride

Composite	Pressure KN	Strength properties		Water Absorption					
				After immersion in boiling water		After immersion in water for 24h		After immersion in water for 7 days	
		Bending strength N/mm ²	Modulus of elasticity N/mm ²	W %	T %	W %	T%	W %	T%
Treated Composite	0	0	0						
	25	4.9	805.7	105	57	96	52	125	70.6
	50	11.3	2640.2	35	14.1	32	14.2	38	15.3

Where W is expressed as a weight and T is a thickness, (polymer percent 20%)

3.3. Effect of aluminum silicate on the composite properties

Aluminum silicate with different concentration (5, 7.5 and 10 %) was added as filler (to fill the spaces between banana fibers) to the treated banana fiber with 20 % polyurethane and then pressed under 50 KN. Table [3] and Figure (3) show that addition of aluminum silicate decreased to an extent the strength properties of the composites while it increases water absorption. This could be attributed to that aluminum silicate interfere with the fiber bonds, forming weak fiber- filler bonds instead of strong fiber – fiber bonds and therefore a decrease in strength properties is expected [8].

Table [3]: Effecting of aluminum silicate on the mechanical and water absorption properties of the treated composite.

Composite	Aluminum Silicate	Strength properties	Water Absorption		
			After immersion in boiling water	After immersion in water for 24h	After immersion in water for 7 days

		Bending strength N/mm ²	Modulus of elasticity N/mm ²	W %	T %	W %	T%	W %	T%
Treated Composite	----	11.3	2640.2	35	14.1	32	14.2	38	15.3
	5	11	2600.3	44	20.6	43	20.6	45	22
	7.5	10.6	2580	50	25	48.6	24.8	50.3	26.4
	10	10.2	2550.6	55.4	32.6	55	31.2	70.3	38

Where W is expressed as a weight and T is a thickness, (polymer percent 20%)

3.4. IR Spectroscopy

As clear from Figure (1), the major difference between the spectra obtained for treated or untreated banana fiber was due to the presence of C = O peak at 1722 Cm⁻¹ in the treated banana fiber [9,10].

Figure (1): IR spectra of untreated (a) and treated (b) composite from banana fiber with maleic anhydride.

3.5. Scanning Electron Microscope

Figures 2 (a, b) showed that the banana fiber – polyurethane composite, treated with a maleic anhydride presents certain adhesion between the fibers and matrix, and has more compact structure than untreated composite.

Figure 2 (c) shows that there are minute cells formed throughout the composites after adding of aluminum silicate. These minute cells decrease to a large extent the free – OH group leading to decrease the dielectric properties of the composites [7].

Figure (2): SEM of the treated (a), untreated composite (b) and treated composite after adding aluminum silicate (c).

3.6. Dielectric studies

Figure 3 (a) shows the relationships between the dielectric constant and polyurethane (PU) concentrations for the treated and untreated composite. This experiment was carried out at different frequencies but the measurements were only represented at 1 KHz. As clear in this figure, the dielectric constant (ϵ') and dielectric loss (ϵ'') of the treated composite showed lower values comparing with that obtained for the untreated composite. This originates from increasing of compatibility between banana fiber and polyurethane due to treatment by maleic anhydride, may result in decrease mobility of dipoles or charge carriers. Consequently, such decrease in ϵ' and ϵ'' of the treated composite is expected. Since, ϵ'' for the treated composite markedly decreased comparing with that obtained for the untreated composite. This result refers to enhancements of the dielectric properties (electrical insulation properties) for the composite treated with maleic anhydride.

For the effect of polyurethane (PU) concentrations on the dielectric properties of composites, it is clear from Figure 3 (a), ϵ' for the untreated composite starts at first to decrease and then it sharply increases with increasing polyurethane at concentrations higher than 20 %. The decrease in ϵ' may be related to that PU is used as crosslinkers connecting the chains of cellulose together which results in a decrease in its mobility. Such decrease in mobility is always associated with decrease in polarization and therefore a decrease in dielectric constant is expected.

Because of the great importance of results concerning that composite containing 20 % PU and treated with maleic anhydride, dielectric experiments were carried out on it, at a wide range of frequency (42Hz – 1MHz) and on adding aluminum silicate (Al_2SiO_5). So, Al_2SiO_5 was added to the treated composite with different concentrations namely; 5, 7.5 and 10 %. Al_2SiO_5 with concentrations lower than 7.5 %, the dielectric constant (ϵ') of the treated composite slightly showed decreased (see figure 7a). Such decrease in ϵ' could be attributed to formation of minute cells throughout the composites⁽⁷⁾ due to addition of aluminum silicate. So, these minute cells decrease to a large extent the free – OH group. On the contrary, at

higher concentrations, abrupt increase in ϵ' is observed indicating an interaction between aluminum silicate and the composite [12].

Figure (3): The dielectric constant ϵ' (a) and dielectric loss ϵ'' (b) of the treated and untreated composite are plotted as a function of polyurethane concentrations. The graph is represented for samples measured at constant frequency (1 KHz).

Figure (4): The dielectric permittivity ϵ' (a) and dielectric loss ϵ'' (b) of the treated composite are plotted as a function of frequency. The graph is represented for sample with 20% polyurethane and loaded with different amount of aluminum silicate.

CONCLUSION

1. For the mechanical measurements, it was found that treatment of the banana fiber by maleic anhydride in addition to increase of polyurethane concentrations and application of high pressure, results in produce composite characterized by high strength properties and lower swelling.
2. For the IR spectroscopy measurements, the treated composite showed a band characterizing C = O of ester group at 1722 Cm⁻¹.
3. For scanning electron microscope measurements, morphology of the treated composite was characterized by a higher compact structure than that obtained for

the untreated composite. Adding of aluminum silicate to the treated composite resulted in forming minute cells throughout the composite.

4. For the dielectric properties measurements, treatment of the banana fiber by maleic anhydride in addition to increase of polyurethane concentrations, the dielectric constant (ϵ') showed increase whereas dielectric loss (ϵ'') showed decrease indicating improvements of dielectric properties of the treated composite. On adding aluminum silicate with concentrations lower than 7.5, the dielectric properties of the treated composite showed decrease. But at higher concentrations, its properties showed abrupt increase.

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